

Numerical Modelling of 3D Printed Cranial Orthoses

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Abstract

The objective of this work is to replace laboratory testing of cranial orthosis design by virtual prototyping using numerical modelling and simulation technologies. In this paper, the focus is put on pre-processing stage of the numerical modelling process. In future Computational Structural Dynamics Simulations will be performed during development of new cranial orthosis design at Invent Medical Group (IMG) company. Stiffness of cranial orthosis will be evaluated by means of numerical modelling and simulation and will replace necessity of physical testing of each and every new design of cranial orthosis to ensure its proper behaviour. Objective of this project is to create a semi-automatic system of mesh generation from the input geometric model based on open source software Netgen Mesh Generator. Geometry of the structure as an input file for meshing is provided in STL format. The output of this project is a software tool which will take a geometric model as an input and produce the finite element mesh with all boundary conditions as an output. The mesh produced is then used for calculation of cranial orthosis stiffness using open source code ESPRESO. Simulation results are verified by comparing with results of the same numerical simulation performed using well-established software package ANSYS and with physical experiment as well.

Introduction

The cranial orthoses are used in children aged 4 to 18 months to correct the plagiocephaly, brachycephaly, and scaphocephaly condition. An asymmetric head shapes are caused by external forces applied to an infant's malleable skull during prenatal/postnatal development or at birth (e.g. multiple-birth infants, sleeping position or premature birth). At an early age, a children's head is growing and changing at a startling rate. The head support using the cranial orthosis is very effective at this time. The orthosis is designed for the individual head shape of the child based on non-invasive scanning. The supporting system consists of plastic shells coupled with a locking mechanism. The stiffness of inner shell – the supporting structure depicted by blue colour in Figure 1 – must be determined based on medical advice.

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Figure 1: Visualisation of the printed cranial orthosis

The aim of this work is to create a virtual prototyping tool to determine the stiffness of supporting structure during a designing process to guarantee its required properties i.e. flexibility. The work in this project was divided into two stages. The first stage was devoted to laboratory testing of one selected structure. The experiment results were used to verify a strongly nonlinear computer model that correctly describes the real structure during physical testing. The obtained knowledge was used in the second stage for idealisation of the model and automation of the whole process. During the second stage, numerical simulations on three variants of structures were performed to test the workflow developed.

Stage I. – Modelling of Laboratory Test

For physical testing of the inner shell of cranial orthosis, a testing device was built (Figure 2). The structures tested are mounted by the clamps and gradually deformed by the plunger. Thin foil between plunger and tested structure was used to minimise friction between them. Deformation of the structure is measured by Vernier calliper.

Figure 2: Testing device

Scheme of the testing process used for numerical model is depicted at Figure 3. Blue colour represents the fixed part of the structure. Plunger is being considered as rigid comparing to the tested structure and friction between plunger and structure is neglected. Loading of the structure is gradual and corresponds to static loading. Tested structure is gradually loaded until maximal loading which equal 5.30 N. This value corresponds to the pressure of a 10cm high column of water. The area on which plunger is in contact with tested structure and thus area where the load is transferred to the structure is depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Scheme of the testing process used for numerical model

Geometry Description

The testing sample of the inner part of the printed cranial orthosis consists of two parts. The first part represents the structure of the inner part of the orthosis. Centre line of this structure has the shape of a spherical segment with constant thickness. The second part, in shape of the circular ring (blue colour in Figure 4) connected to the structure, is used for prescribing boundary conditions corresponding to the clamping of the physical structure at testing device.

Figure 4: Geometry of the numerical model

The geometry of the structure is provided in the STL format. An STL file format describes unstructured triangulated surface by vertices (ordered by the right-hand rule) of the triangle and its normal in a three-dimensional Cartesian Coordinate System. In our case the origin of the global coordinate system is placed at the centre of the circular ring with the y axis aligned with its axis of the rotation facing upwards. By definition STL, format does not contain information about the size of the objects, so the units are arbitrary.

Material properties

The material used for inner part of the cranial orthosis is HP 3D High Reusability PA 12 widely used in engineering industry. In our calculations, this material is considered to be isotropic with linear elastic behaviour. Mechanical properties for linear elastic model are listed in Table 1.

Mechanical property	Value
Young modulus	1 500 MPa
Poisson ratio	0.39

Table 1: Mechanical property of PA12

Validation of the numerical model

Before the creation of the semi-automatic system of mesh generation, a validation of the numerical model and fine tuning of input parameters using software package ANSYS was performed. The geometry of the structure and the plunger in STL format was imported and finite element mesh containing tetrahedral elements was created. Sensitivity analysis was performed and based on its results, maximal size of element edge was set to 0.20 mm. Number of nodes and elements of this numerical model are listed in Table 2.

Nodes	1 257 000
Elements	5 012 000

Table 2: Number of nodes and elements of numerical model

Boundary conditions for simulation were prescribed as follows:

- for all nodes belonging to the circular ring (highlighted by blue colour in Figure 4) all degrees of freedom were restricted
- contact between tested structure and plunger was considered as frictionless
- for all nodes of plunger's top surface only vertical movement was allowed
- for all nodes of plunger's top surface force 5.30 N with linear increase was prescribed

To correctly represent physical behaviour of the printed structure and to be able to capture its large deformation and deflection higher order finite elements for spatial discretisation were used in numerical model. Resulting numerical model, including inequality constrains, consists of 3.8 million Degrees Of Freedom (DOF). Solution of this problem was done on common workstation with 16 cores. Time needed for solving non-linear problem was 29.6 h. Total deflection of centre of the tested structure was 5.22 mm (see Figure 5 for reference)

Figure 5: Total deflection of test sample [mm]

Comparisons of numerical results with physical experiment are listed in Table 3. It could be seen that difference is less than 20% which could be considered as satisfactory considering that we are dealing with highly non-linear material. To increase agreement between numerical and physical model, the numerical model would have to describe more precisely clamping of the tested sample and a series of physical tests on PA 12 to obtain its material properties would have to be performed. However, for comparison of different designs of the inner part of the printed cranial orthosis this refinement is unnecessary and that for this purpose linear elastic behaviour without large deformation formulation will suffice.

	Test sample
Laboratory testing	6.30 mm
ANSYS	5.22 mm

Table 3: Comparison of maximum deflection with laboratory testing

Stage II. –Automation of Calculations

Based on the results of a numerical simulation of the inner part of the printed cranial orthosis mentioned above, the simplification that reduce time consumption of solving numerical model is necessary. Following simplifications were proposed:

- non-linear behaviour will not be considered and linear elastic simulation will be performed
- numerical model will not consist of circular ring and boundary conditions will be enforced on inner part of the printed cranial orthosis directly

The simplification of the geometry will be done before it is exported into STL format which is used as an input format for mesh generation. The geometry of a simplified model is depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Simplified geometry of inner part of the printed cranial orthosis

Finite Element Mesh generation by Netgen mesh generator

The exported geometrical model in STL format is used as an input for Netgen mesh generator. The geometry of the objects is described in form of triangles representing surface in this file geometry. This original surface mesh could be used only for visualisation purposes. For purpose of the numerical simulation it must be pre-processed and new mesh must be created.

To generate new meshes (wire, surface and volume finite element mesh) more suitable for numerical simulations, Netgen mesh generator is used. For purpose of this project a new procedure named **mesher_vol** was created by modifying the existing C++ Netgen library template. This procedure takes STL file as an input (`Ng_STL_LoadGeometry(argv[1]);`) and creates wire (`Ng_STL_MakeEdges(stl_geom, mesh, &mp);`), surface (`Ng_STL_GenerateSurfaceMesh(stl_geom, mesh, &mp);`) and volume (`Ng_GenerateVolumeMesh(mesh, &mp);`) finite element mesh base on the geometry described in this file. It also creates the geometrical entities composed by elements of the surface mesh. The geometrical entities are sorted out in the mesh pre-processing phase in such a way that two global sets of the nodes for application of the boundary conditions could be created.

After the mesh is generated by Netgen meshing kernel, the resulting mesh is outputted into Netgen native file format with *.vol file extension. The required properties of the mesh such as the maximal length of the element edge are specified by the user. In our case, the maximal length of the element edge was set to 0.20 mm. This value was determined by mesh sensitivity analysis as mentioned above. The procedure for mesh generation was tested on three different geometries of the inner part of the printed cranial orthosis provided in form of STL files. The details of the meshes generated on those geometries are depicted in Figure 7, and the number of nodes and elements for each mesh are listed in Table 4.

Figure 7: Finite element mesh on three different geometries of inner part of the printed cranial orthosis (Geometry 1 on the left, Geometry 2 in the middle and Geometry 3 on the right)

	Geometry 1	Geometry 2	Geometry 3
Nodes	724 000	682 000	580 000
Elements	2 205 000	2 237 000	1 808 000

Table 4: Statistic of the finite element meshes

Mesh Pre-processing

For semi-automatic virtual testing of the inner part of the printed cranial orthosis during the design phase, the whole process, from the mesh generation, through the application of the boundary conditions, solution of the numerical model, to the post-processing must be performed without any user intervention. To fulfil this requirement, the generated mesh must be pre-processed in such a way that geometrical entities for applying boundary condition are identified. Two sets of the elements or element faces will be identified. First set (marked by blue colour in Figure 8) will be used to prescribe displacement boundary conditions. This will represent mounting of the inner part of the printed cranial orthosis. Second set (marked by red colour in Figure 8), will be used for loading the structure by constant pressure.

Figure 8: Preparing sets for application of boundary condition

Mesh pre-processing is performed in several steps employing the Python scripts and *NumPy* library. First finite element mesh in Netgen native format is loaded into the matrix structures by **reader_vol.py** script. Relevant parts of this script are described below:

```

n_sur_ele = int(f.readline())
ng_sur_ele = np.fromfile(f,count=n_sur_ele*11,sep=" ").reshape((n_sur_ele,11))
n_vol_ele = int(f.readline())
ng_vol_ele = np.fromfile(f,count=n_vol_ele*6,sep=" ").reshape((n_vol_ele,6))
n_nodes = int(f.readline())
ng_nodes = np.fromfile(f,count=n_nodes*3,sep=" ").reshape((n_nodes,3))
nodes = ng_nodes
elems_sur = np.zeros((len(ng_sur_ele),4),dtype=int)
elems_sur[:,0] = ng_sur_ele[:,1]
elems_sur[:,1] = ng_sur_ele[:,5]
elems_sur[:,2] = ng_sur_ele[:,6]
elems_sur[:,3] = ng_sur_ele[:,7]

elems_vol = np.zeros((len(ng_vol_ele),4),dtype=int)
elems_vol[:,0] = ng_vol_ele[:,2]
elems_vol[:,1] = ng_vol_ele[:,3]
elems_vol[:,2] = ng_vol_ele[:,4]
elems_vol[:,3] = ng_vol_ele[:,5]

```

Next, individual parts of the surface mesh are divided into the individual groups of geometrical entities using **extractor_set_entities.py** script. Excerpt of this script is described below:

```

n_set_faces = int(max(elems_sur[:,0]))
set_faces = np.zeros((n_set_faces, n_sur_ele / 3),dtype=int)
count_set_faces = np.zeros((n_set_faces), dtype=np.int)

for k in range(n_sur_ele):
    if elems_sur[k,0] == count_groups+1:
        set_faces[count_groups,count_set_faces[count_groups]] = k+1
        count_set_faces[count_groups] = count_set_faces[count_groups] + 1
    elif elems_sur[k,0] == count_groups+2:
        count_groups = count_groups + 1
        set_faces[count_groups,count_set_faces[count_groups]] = k+1
        count_set_faces[count_groups] = count_set_faces[count_groups] + 1
    elif elems_sur[k,0] != count_groups+2: # podminka pokud nejsou v poradi

        for i in range(n_set_faces):
            if elems_sur[k,0] == i + 1:
                count_groups2 = i
                set_faces[count_groups2,count_set_faces[count_groups2]] = k+1
                count_set_faces[count_groups2] = count_set_faces[count_groups2] + 1
        break
set_faces = set_faces[:,0:max(count_set_faces)]

```

Next, the normal direction of every surface element is established. The allocation of the geometrical entities and corresponding surface elements to one of two global sets (for application of the boundary conditions) is done with **selector_set_faces.py** script.

The identification of the geometrical entities representing the part of the structure where fixed boundary conditions will be applied is based on the following conditions:

- The coordinate of one node of the arbitrary element from the geometrical entity coordinates falls into the interval (0, tol_fix_y), where tol_fix_y is the tolerance in millimetres defined by the user
- The angle between the element normal and the vector connecting the origin of the coordinate system to any node of this element falls into the interval (0, tol_fix_deg) where tol_fix_deg is the tolerance in degrees defined by user
- If both criteria are fulfilled, this geometrical entity and all elements corresponding to this entity are added to the set where the fixed boundary condition will be applied

The step described above is performed for all geometrical entities. Using the geometrical entities instead of element itself is used to speed up the whole process because selection process does not have to go through all the elements but only through all the geometrical entities.

```

for i in range(n_set_faces):
    node_null = np.array([0,0,0])
    node_axis = np.array([0,1,0])
    select_node1 = elems_sur[set_faces[i,0]-1,1]
    select_node2 = elems_sur[set_faces[i,0]-1,2]
    select_node3 = elems_sur[set_faces[i,0]-1,3]
    tol_y = 0.70 #mm

    # angle
    u = nodes[select_node1-1] - node_null
    v = norms[set_faces[i,0]-1]

    cos_angle = (u[0]*v[0]+u[1]*v[1]+u[2]*v[2])/(math.sqrt(u[0]**2+u[1]**2+u[2]**2)*math.sqrt(v[0]**2+v[1]**2+v[2]**2))
    deg_angle= np.degrees(math.acos(cos_angle))

    tol_angle = 44 #deg

    if nodes[select_node1-1,1] < tol_y:
        if nodes[select_node2-1,1] < tol_y:
            if nodes[select_node3-1,1] < tol_y:
                if abs(deg_angle) < tol_angle:

                    selected_set_faces[0,count_selector] = i+1
                    count_selector = count_selector + 1

    for i in range(count_selector):
        for k in range(count_set_faces[selected_set_faces[0,i]-1]):
            set_faces_fixed[0,counter_fixed_face] = set_faces[selected_set_faces[0,i]-1,k]
            counter_fixed_face = counter_fixed_face + 1

```

A constant pressure is applied on the two geometrical entities containing the most surface elements. Those two entities represent outer and inner part of the structure and their denomination is based on the normal direction. This is done by checking the normal of the arbitrary element from one of the geometrical entity.

```

for i in range(0,len(count_set_faces)):
if count_set_faces[i] > hi:
    mi = hi
    max2 = max1
    hi = count_set_faces[i]
    max1 = i
elif count_set_faces[i] < hi and count_set_faces[i] > mi:
    mi = count_set_faces[i]
    max2 = i

tol_angle_presure = 90 #deg
node_null = np.array([0,0,0])
node_axis = np.array([0,-1,0])
norm_max2 = norms[set_faces[max2,0]-1]
u = node_axis - node_null
v = norm_max2
cos_angle = (u[0]*v[0]+u[1]*v[1]+u[2]*v[2])/(math.sqrt(u[0]**2+u[1]**2+u[2]**2)*math.sqrt(v[0]**2+v[1]**2+v[2]**2))
deg_angle= np.degrees(math.acos(cos_angle))
selected_faces_presure = max2

if abs(deg_angle) > tol_angle_presure: # checking normal
    selected_faces_presure = max1

set_faces_presure = set_faces[selected_faces_presure,0:count_set_faces[selected_faces_presure]]

```

Because boundary conditions will be applied to the nodes not to the surface elements, the set of nodes corresponding to the particular element have to be extracted by **extractor_set_nodes.py** script.

```

# fixed DOF boundary conditions
set_nodes_fixed = np.zeros((1,n_sur_ele*n_nodes), dtype=np.int)
count_sets = np.zeros((1), dtype=np.int)

for k in range(counter_fixed_face):
    set_nodes_fixed[0,3*count_sets[0]:3*count_sets[0]+3] = elems_sur[set_faces_fixed[0,k]-1,1:4]
    count_sets[0] = count_sets[0] + 1

set_nodes_fixed = set_nodes_fixed[:,0:3*max(count_sets)]
set_nodes_fixed = np.unique(set_nodes_fixed)

# pressure boundary conditions
set_nodes_presure = np.zeros((1,n_sur_ele*n_nodes), dtype=np.int)
count_sets = np.zeros((1), dtype=np.int)

for k in range(count_set_faces[selected_faces_presure]):
    set_nodes_presure[0,3*count_sets[0]:3*count_sets[0]+3] = elems_sur[set_faces_presure[k]-1,1:4]
    count_sets[0] = count_sets[0] + 1

set_nodes_presure = set_nodes_presure[:,0:3*max(count_sets)]
set_nodes_presure = np.unique(set_nodes_presure)

```

After all those steps, all the information is outputted into the file which could be read by software package Ansys. The above described workflow is depicted in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Workflow for semi-automatic mesh generation and numerical model solution

Numerical simulation

After the finite element mesh is created and pre-processed, the solution of the numerical model can be performed. In our case, open source ESPRESSO is used. This open source code will read all the information from the files created by **writer_cdb.py** script and performs simulation. Results of the total deflection of the three variants of the inner part of the cranial orthosis are depicted in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Total deflection [mm] of the idealized structures, from left view, Geometry 1, 2 and 3

Comparison of the results obtained from open source code ESPRESSO and software package Ansys for all three geometries is listed in Table 5.

Geometry	1	2	3
ESPRESO	8.035 mm	8.868 mm	15.55 mm
ANSYS	8.035 mm	8.868 mm	15.55 mm

Table 5: Comparison of maximum deflection calculated by ESPRESO and Ansys

After the validation of the results, scalability test using ESPRESO was performed. For scalability tests, the numerical model representing Geometry 1 was used. Numerical model consisting of 2.2 million DOF was solved on common work station with 16 cores. This simulation took 42 s. Next scalability test on the Salomon cluster employing 1 to 4 compute nodes was performed. Solution times are listed in Table 6 and depicted in Figure 11.

Cores [-]	Computational time [s]
24	19
48	9.0
96	6.1

Table 6: Scalability test on Salomon cluster

Figure 11: Scalability of the task on Salomon cluster

Conclusion

The results presented in this paper demonstrate that physical testing of the cranial orthosis could be very effectively replaced by virtual prototyping using numerical modelling and simulation techniques. The semi-automated workflow for the mesh generation, the solution of the numerical model and the output of results have been developed and could be implemented into the design cycle of cranial orthosis. It was also demonstrated that the commercial software packages could be effectively substituted by open source alternatives without compromising on fidelity of the results.

References

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